

Standard Operating Procedure

SOP/ENL/02/1.0

**Semi-static Mussel
Bioconcentration Test**

Version: 1.0

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I. Purpose

The purpose of this SOP is to document the procedures of the semi-static bioconcentration test with mussels.

II. Objective of the test

The objective of this test is to evaluate the bioconcentration of nanomaterials in mussels in a semi-static exposure.

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III. Validity of the test

For the test results to be valid, the following criteria apply:

- Mortality in the control test chambers is not higher than 10% at the end of the test.

IV. Description of the method

a. Equipment and material

The following equipment and material are needed to perform the test:

- Glass tanks.
- Plastic tubing and aeration stones.
- Equipment for determination of water parameters such as: conductivity, pH, temperature, salinity, dissolved oxygen, ammonia and nitrites.
- Fish net.
- Glass graduated flasks and cylinders.
- Scale.
- Scalpel, knife and scissors.
- Weighing boats.
- Dental wax.
- Aquarium syphon.

b. Test organisms

Test organisms should be adult mussels (*Mytilus* spp) acquire already depurated from a reliable source.

c. Test chambers

Test chambers should be glass tanks, equipped with an aeration stone. Tanks should be randomly positioned. At least three tanks should be used for each concentration.

d. Water and test conditions

Test water should be treated seawater or artificial seawater with a salinity of 35 ppm (± 2 ppm).

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Tanks should be placed in a temperature controlled room and temperature should be maintained at 17°C (\pm 2°C). The photoperiod should be of 14:10 (L:D).

e. Feeding

Mussels should be fed three times a week with the marine algae *Tisochrysis lutea*. Final concentration in the tank should be of 10⁵ algae cells/ml.

f. Duration of test

The test should have a duration of 28 days. The first day of exposure should be considered day zero.

V. Acclimatization of organisms

After arriving at the laboratory, the mussels should be placed in a tray filled with ice and seawater.

Before being distributed to the test chambers all the mussels have to be cleaned and their viability evaluated.

The mussels are acclimatized in the final test chambers. Forty five mussels should randomly be placed in each tank. At least one extra tank with excess mussels is maintained to replace any dead mussel during acclimation.

During this phase, water should be changed when necessary and the mussels fed three times a week.

VI. Procedure

a. Controls

A negative control should be used consisting only of seawater.

If a solvent is used to disperse the nanomaterials a solvent control is required.

b. Test concentrations

Two relevant test concentrations (when available, close to the Predicted Environmental Concentration) that do not induce mortality should be used. The nanomaterial stock solution should be dispersed as needed and, when possible,

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the test concentrations prepared in seawater. The dispersions should be mixed with the algae before added to the tanks.

c. Start of test

At the beginning of the test (day zero), all the water should be removed from the tanks and the necessary mussels for this timepoint are sampled. After, the tanks should be filled with seawater until a level of approximately 80% of the final volume. At this point, the mix of algae and the nanomaterials should be added to each tank, in the respective concentration. Only algae are added to the negative control tanks.

The tanks are then filled with the missing volume of seawater and the water parameters measured.

d. Water renewals

Water should be renewed 3 times a week in the following schedule:

Table 1. Schedule of water renewal, feeding and addition of nanomaterials

Days	Percentage of renewal	Feeding	Addition of nanomaterials
Mondays	25%	Yes	No
Wednesdays	100%	Yes	Yes
Fridays	25%	Yes	No

On Mondays and Fridays, the respective water parameters must be measured, 25% of the water replaced with seawater and algae added to each aquarium. On Wednesdays, the respective water parameters should be measured. All the water should be removed and replaced according to the procedure described for the beginning of the test. Thirty minutes after the addition of the algae and nanoparticles a water sample should be collected and maintained at 4°C until processed for nanomaterials quantification.

e. Water Quality Measurements

Water parameters in the tanks should be measured in the following schedule:

Table 2. Schedule of water parameters measurements

Parameters	Frequency	Measurements
Temperature Salinity pH	At least 4 times a week	In one tank of each concentration
Conductivity Dissolved oxygen	Day 0 and 28	In all tanks
Temperature Salinity pH Conductivity Dissolved oxygen Ammonia Nitrites	Once a week	In all tanks

Throughout the test the parameters should be maintained within the following ranges:

Table 3. Acceptable ranges for the water parameters

Parameters	Range
Temperature	17°C ± 2°C
Salinity	35 ppm ± 2 ppm
pH	7.5 – 9.5
Dissolved oxygen	≥ 80 %

f. Mussel's sampling

Sampling of mussels should be performed at the following schedule:

Table 4. Schedule of mussels sampling during the test

Analysis	Timepoint (days)	Number of mussels
Quantification	0, 1, 7, 14, 21, 28	5
Electron microscopy	0, 1, 7, 14, 21, 28	1
Optical microscopy	0, 14, 28	1

The mussels are sampled and placed in ice until the processing. Maximum length, maximum width of the shell and weight with the shell (total weight) are measured. After that, the mussels should be opened and the organisms carefully removed from the shell and weight without it (flesh weight).

Dead mussels are not weighted and are discarded after measurement.

Quantification and optical microscopy sample preparation

After de-shelled and weighted, the total soft tissue is preserved at -20°C until sample preparation for quantification. In the case of optical microscopy, the organisms are fixated in formalin 10% solution neutral buffered for 48h with a total replacement of the formalin 10% after 24h. After 48h the fixative must be replaced for 70% ethanol to preserved the sample until continue to a routine processing for optical microscopy analysis

Electron microscopy samples preparation

For the transmission electron microscopy analysis, the mussels should be carefully opened and samples of the mantle, gills and digestive gland collected. The samples should be cut in squares of approximately 0.5-1 mm³ and then placed on Karnovsky fixative. After 24h at 4°C the fixative should be replaced by sodium cacodylate buffer 0.1 M. The weight of the mussels without the shell should be accessed and the remaining organisms can be discarded. On the last day of sampling (day 28), the shells from these mussels should be left to dry completely for further analysis by scanning electron microscopy.

VII. Data analysis

The Bioconcentration factor (BCF) should be calculated at the end of exposure by applying the following formula:

$$BCF = \text{Conc}_{\text{mussels}} / \text{Conc}_{\text{water}}$$

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Appropriated statistical methods should be applied to detect differences between the controls and the concentrations of exposure for the overall survival of the mussels, for the morphometric parameters and as also for the bioconcentration data.